

FOOT AND MOUTH DISEASE IN INDIA: CHALLENGES AND ROADMAP FOR ERADICATION

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Abstract-

Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) is a highly contagious viral disease of cloven-hoofed animal, causing significant economic losses in India. The main route for its spread is through direct contact of the animal. There is substantial decrease in the milk yield and increased abortion in animals. CFT, ELISA, FAT and Neutralization are the main tests performed for diagnosing this disease. Various programs have been launched by the Indian government which have become very helpful in controlling and spreading this dangerous viral disease.

Keywords: Foot and mouth disease, India, Livestock, Eradication, Vaccination

Introduction –

Foot-and-mouth disease is a contagious viral infection that affects cloven-hoofed animals like cattle, sheep, goat & pigs. FMD is caused by FMD virus which belongs to genus Aphovirus and Picornaviridae family. FMD is mainly characterized by development of vesicular lesion on mouth, feet & mammary gland. FMD has serious economic effect on livestock industries. There are seven serotypes (O, A, C, SAT1, SAT2, SAT3, Asia 1). The symptoms shown by affected animals are fever, excessive salivation and lameness. Recovered animals lose their productivity for a long time. They also act as carriers which transmit the virus without showing any symptoms. It is so contagious that it is concern for veterinary microbiology and public health and requires continuous research for effective vaccines.

Distribution-

The disease was first recorded in Europe in 1548. The first outbreak was documented in 1839 in the Netherlands. The disease is absent in America, the United Kingdom, North Australia & New Zealand. Since 1989, the USA is free from FMD.[18]

In Asia, FMD is prevalent in India, Sri Lanka, Nepal & Burma. Countries like Japan, Australia, Mongolia, and New Zealand are free from FMD. The outbreak of “O” is continuously reported from India, Pakistan, China, and Sri Lanka.

In India FMD is endemic.

Causative agents- FMD virus is a filterable virus. It belongs to the family Picornaviridae, which has approximate size of 8-10 µm. It is one of the smallest viruses. It is ss positive sense having 8500 nucleotides in length. It has an icosahedral capsid.

Serotypes

There are mainly six antigenic serotypes O (Oise), A (Alemand), Asia-1, SAT-1, SAT-2, SAT-3 (Southern African Territories) are prevalent. Serotype C of FMD virus has actually no longer reported in field outbreaks worldwide since 2004 [19]. Different strains are now identified based on ELISA, RT-PCR, and nucleotide sequence.

Susceptible Host

Cattle are more susceptible to FMD. Buffalo, sheep and goat are also affected. Wild animals like deer, boar, black buck, nilgai, pig, and elephants are also affected. Rabbits, Guinea pigs, chicks can be artificially infected. Crossbred cattle are more sensitive to FMD in comparison to Zebu cattle.

There are 109.85 million buffalo, 74.26 million Sheep, 142.88 million goats, 9.06 million pigs, 0.39 million Mithun, and 0.06 million yaks which are susceptible to FMD[25].

Modes of Transmission

Mainly through direct contact with the animal. Spread is through ingestion via the digestive tract.

Clothes, bedding, and feeding material like hay and straw can be infected by this virus and act as a source of contamination. The virus may also be present in meat and bone. Urine, milk, faeces, and body secretions may also infect healthy animals. Visitors can also spread this to healthy animals.

FMD virus can live in the environment mostly when there are moist and cool conditions. It is suggested that cattle serve as indicators, sheep as maintenance, and pigs as amplifier hosts.[22]

The incubation period of FMD is highly variable, 2-14 days and it is dependent on the route of transmission, species of the animal, dose and strain of virus and the husbandry conditions [1]. It is found that in cattle period of infectiousness is 1.7 days and are not infectious until 0.5 days after the appearance of clinical signs [5].

Economic loss due to FMD outbreaks-

Contribution of GDP (Gross Domestic Product) by livestock in agriculture sector is 25.6% and 4.11% to National GDP [8].

FMD infection results in drop in production of milk yield (minimum 25%), increased abortion in pregnant animals. Semen quality of bulls is affected. Decreased wool production in sheep.

The total economic loss due to FMD In India exceeds 25,000 crores (USD 3.1 billion) annually [13] [23]. This includes losses from reduced productivity treatment costs, and indirect losses due to restrictions on animal trade & exports.

In a recent report the total farm level economic loss due to FMD in India was estimated at USD 2768 million (INR 221,110 million), USD 237 million (INR 18,910 million), USD 133 million respectively during the severe, moderate and mild outbreak settings[12].

Clinical sign and Symptoms-

The incubation period of this disease is 2-8 days. This may be extended for 2-3 weeks. Temperature in the animal affected may range from 104°F -106°F. There is decrease in milk production. Vesicles appear in the oral mucosa, udder and interdigital space. Drooling of saliva and sometimes protrusion of tongue may be observed. The animal become anorectic and dull. Large vesicle may be seen in digital skin and this may produce lameness and pain. Signs of gastroenteritis may be seen in some animals. Death in calves may be due to myocarditis. Morbidity is 100% but mortality is less in zebu cattle as compared to cross bred cattle. The severity depends upon strain of the virus and individual immunity of the animal.

Diagnosis-

Complement Fixation Test (C.F.T.) - It is a serological test to detect the presence of antibodies against the FMD vims in animal samples. If the antigenic material is good this test will provide result within 2-3 hours.

A known amount of FMD virus and complement is combined with serum samples from suspected FMD cases. Antibodies will attach to the virus and fix the complement if they are present, stopping haemolysis. The existence or lack of antibodies against FMD virus is subsequently determined by evaluating the degree of haemolysis.

The sensitivity and specificity of CFT are typically not as high as those of contemporary techniques like ELISA and RT-PCR.

ELISA- It is based on the antigen-antibody interaction. When a sample of suspected FMD virus is added, the antigen binds to formed antibodies. Samples are diluted and added to wells coated with specific antibodies against FMD virus. Following incubation materials unbound are removed by washing. A substrate that generate visible signal is added after a secondary enzyme-linked antibody. The intensity of signal correlates with the amount of antigen in the sample. The test has been found to give higher percentage of positive typing over C.F.T. and is quite sensitive [21][23].

Fluorescent Antibody Test (F.A.T.)- The F.A.T. utilizes antibodies tagged with fluorescent dyes that bind exclusively to the FMD virus antigens present in tissue samples or vesicular fluids. When exposed to UV light, these antibodies exhibit fluorescence, confirming the presence of virus. Vesicular fluid or epithelial tissue are collected from the affected animal are prepared on slides. The labelled antibodies are applied to these slides for binding to FMD virus present. The slides are examined under a fluorescence microscope. If fluorescence is present this indicates the positive result of FMD virus. Microscopy reveal fluorescein differing from the vesicular disease viruses[16].

Neutralization Test -Finding out if an animal has been exposed to the virus and produced an immunological response - whether it has protective antibodies against the virus- is the aim of the test. Suckling mice or tissue culture is used as the test medium. Serotypes Known O, A, C and Asia -1 are used as antigens. FMD virus produces both early 19s and late 7s antibodies[6].

Roadmap for control & prevention of FMD in India-

Various initiatives have been taken by the government of India to minimize the risk and spread of the disease. Large-scale vaccination programme for eradication of this disease is encouraged for eradication of this disease. Strict quarantine and slaughter practices are also employed.

The bedding material of the affected animal is to be destroyed either by burial or by burning. Complete destruction of the premises should be done. There are various programmes launched by Indian government in order to combat this disease.

1.FMD Control program (FMDCP)-

This program was launched during 10th five-year plan (2002-2007) a Central Scheme. It was expanded over the years. This programme mainly focussed in controlling FMD in cattle, buffalo and Mithun. The main component of FMDCP was biannual vaccination. This vaccine covered Serotypes O, A, and Asia 1.

Along with this vaccination monitoring was encouraged. This involved collecting the pre and post vaccination samples for checking the antibody levels in animals.

2. Livestock Health and Disease Control Programme (LHDCP)

This program covers FMD and also provide measures for disease like PPR and classical swine fever. It mainly focussed on vaccination and disease surveillance.

3. National Animal Disease Control Programme (NADCP) -

VACCINATION	AGE
Primary Vaccination	4 months
Booster	2-4 weeks later
Revaccination	Every 6 months

2. Foot and Mouth disease vaccine (Hoescht India Limited)-

It contains FMD virus type O, A, C, Asia-1 which is adsorbed on aluminium hydroxide and gets inactivated. It is used for the immunization of cattle, buffalo, sheep and goat. 10 ml by subcutaneous route is given in cattle, buffalo and calves while in sheep and goat dose is 5 ml.

Vaccination	Age
Initial	3 weeks and above

This programme was launched in September 2019 controlling two major livestock disease- FMD and Brucellosis. The main objectives of this program are to control the FMD by 2025 and eradication of FMD by 2030. This programme aimed at increasing the domestic production of milk by significant decrease in disease. This scheme is fully funded by central government with 100% financial assistance to all states of India and union territories. This program has also focused on the vaccination of female calves between 4-8 months of age for the brucellosis disease.

Vaccines-

Different types of vaccines have been tried against FMD disease. The vaccines that are present cannot provide guaranteed protection against FMD [3]. Vaccines that are used:

1. Formalized Virus Vaccine

- Vallee Carre and Riyard in France in 1926 developed this vaccine.
- This virus is grown under controlled conditions. Once it has grown, it is harvested and inactivated by formalin. About 0.04% to 0.05% formalin concentration is used.
- This vaccine completely inactivates the virus particles.

2. Formalized Aluminium hydroxide gel vaccine

- This vaccine was firstly prepared by Waldmann (1938).
- This vaccine is prepared by harvesting the virus on tongue epithelium of cattle. The epithelium is scraped, emulsified in normal saline and then virus is adsorbed on aluminium hydroxide gel. It is then treated with 0.05% formalin for two days at 25°C.
- It is mainly injected through subcutaneous route.
- It mainly provides immunity for 6-8 months.
- Dose 2-5 ml depending on the animal species.
- It requires storage at 2-8°C.
- This vaccine provides immunity for a shorter period of time. There is possibility of accumulation of aluminium at the injection site.

3. Crystal Violet Vaccine-

- This vaccine was first developed by G. Graub in 1939 in Switzerland.
- The virus is harvested in the tongue of the animal and then scraping is done. After the emulsification, suspension is centrifuged and supernatant is collected which then gets mixed with the blood of donor cattle. This is then mixed with crystal violet to make 0.03% of crystal violet is added for making the final concentration. Incubation is done at 37°C for 8 days.
- This vaccine is mainly given by subcutaneous route. The final vaccine has a violet colour.
- It requires Storage at 2-8°C.
- This provides immunity for approximately 1-1.5 years.

Commercial polyvalent vaccines in India:

1. Raksha FMD Vaccine (Indian Immunologicals)

It contains FMD virus type O, C, Asia-1 and A-22.

The vaccine is inactivated by aziridine compound.

Dose of cattle, buffalo and calves is 3 ml by subcutaneous route.

In sheep and goat dose is 1 ml by subcutaneous route.

Booster	Within 3 months of initial vaccination
Revaccination	Every six months.

3. Foot and Mouth disease vaccine (BAIF Institute of Animal Health)-

This vaccine contains O, A, C, Asia-1 and monovalent subtype A-22 strains of viruses.

Dose in cattle, buffalo and calf is 10 ml while in sheep and goat it is 5 ml.

Primary Vaccination	Booster	Revaccination
Calves (6-8 weeks old)	4 months age and 6 months later	At 6, 9, 12 months interval
Young animals (4-6 months old)	6 months later	
Adult animals	3-4 months	

Conclusion-

The fight against FMD in India presents challenges towards eradication. FMD being a major threat to livestock which causes economic loss, there is urgency for effective control measures. Ongoing National Animal Disease Control Program (NADCP) have shown positive results resulting in decrease in disease incidence. To achieve the goal for FMD- free India by 2030 there is requirement of intricate approach. Vaccination strategies, disease monitoring and surveillance needs to be improved. Collaboration of farmers with government agencies will helpful in early eradication of FMD disease from India.

References-

- Alexandersen, S., & Mowat, N. (2005). Foot-and-mouth disease: Host range and pathogenesis.
- Brooksby, J. B. (1967). Foot-and-mouth disease—a world problem.
- Brooksby, J. B. (1981). Genetic engineering and foot and mouth disease vaccines. *Nature*, 289(5798), 535. <https://doi.org/10.1038/289535a0>
- Chakraborty, A. (2021). A textbook of preventive veterinary medicine.
- Charleston, B., Reid, S. M., & S. A. A. (2011). Relationship between clinical signs and transmission of an infectious disease: Foot-and-mouth disease in cattle. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(29), 11548-11553. doi:10.1073/pnas.1101218108.
- Cowan, K. M., & Graves, J. H. (1965). Sensitivity of cell cultures, cattle, mice, and guinea-pigs for detection of nineteen foot-and-mouth disease viruses. *Bulletin of the Office International des Épizooties*, 63(5), 1237–1243. <https://doi.org/10.20506/bull.oie.1965.63.5.1237>
- Cowan, K. M., & Graves, J. H. (1966). A third antigenic component associated with foot-and-mouth disease infection. *Virology*, 30, 528–540. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0042-6822\(66\)90128-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0042-6822(66)90128-1)
- Dash, S. (2017). Contribution of livestock sector to Indian economy. *Indian Journal of Research*, 6(1), 890–891.
- Dash, S. (2017). Foot-and-mouth disease virus transmission dynamics and persistence in a herd of vaccinated dairy cattle in India.
- Economic impact of foot-and-mouth disease on India's livestock sector (2015). *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences*.
- Foot-and-mouth disease status in India during the second decade of the twenty-first century (2011–2020). Research article in PubMed Central.
- Govindaraj, G., Ganesh Kumar, B., Krishnamohan, A., Hegde, R., Kumar, N., Prabhakaran, K., Wadhwan, V. M., Kakker, N., Lokhande, T., Sharma, K., & others. (2021). Foot and mouth disease (FMD) incidence in cattle and buffaloes and its associated farm-level economic costs in endemic India. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 190, 105318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2021.105318>
- ICAR-National Institute of Foot and Mouth Disease (ICAR-NIFMD). Capacity building series: Capacity building programme for district level officers.
- Kumar, S. (1973): Annual Report of Programme Coordinator. All India Co-ordinated Research Project for Epidemiological Studies on Foot and Mouth Disease.
- Minett, F.C. (1948). Panting in cattle - A sequel to foot-and-mouth disease.
- Mohanty & Cottral (1970). Foot-and-mouth disease virus: Rapid assay using the fluorescent antibody technique.
- McVicar JW, Suttmoller P (1976). Growth of foot-and-mouth disease virus in the upper respiratory tract of non-immunized, vaccinated, and recovered cattle after intranasal inoculation. *Journal of Hygiene*, 76(3), 467-481.
- OIE, New Delhi Meeting 1997.
- Paton et al. (2021). The history of foot-and-mouth disease virus serotype C: The first known extinct serotype? *Virus Evolution*, 7(1), veab009.
- Press Information Bureau (PIB). Vaccinations against foot & mouth disease completed in around 24 crore cattle and buffaloes across the country.
- Roeder, P.L., & Le Blank Smith, J. (1987). Detection and typing of foot-and-mouth disease virus by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay: A sensitive, rapid and reliable technique for primary diagnosis.
- Seller, I., & Parker, J.B. (1969). Airborne excretion of foot-and-mouth disease virus.
- Srinivasan, K., & others. (2015). Economic impact of foot-and-mouth disease on India's livestock sector.
- Warner, I.M., Callis, J.B., Davidson., Gouterman, M., & Christian, G.D. (1975). Fluorescence Analysis: A New Approach. *Analytical Letters*, 8(9), 665–681.
- 20th Livestock Census 2019 Department of Animal Husbandry and Dairy Dairying (DAHD), Govt. of India , <https://www.dahd.nic.in>